

PLAN4CET

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PLAN4CET

Cities and urban areas have been identified as the main opportunity in reaching climate neutrality, as they consume 78% of the world’s energy and produce more than 60% of GHG. This need and vision are shared across EU cities and regions, but the climate neutrality transition process is complex, and many barriers have been identified. Even if local and regional authorities have shown commitment to achieve climate neutrality, the lack of appropriate horizontal and vertical **Clean Energy Transition (CET)** governance, integrated and holistic solutions and lack capacity (knowledge and resources) to develop and implement CET plans and strategies slows down the development of these process.

The general objective of the PLAN4CET project is to support European regions and cities to design, develop and implement CET plans according to their needs and possibilities. To do so, the project has been conceived as an initiative where different project outputs (methodologies, tools and capability building and technical assistance) will be generated to support EU regions (specially to support medium and small municipalities with a capacity lack) and cities in their CET planning, implementation and monitoring activities. The project will directly support 3 EU regions in improving the Climate and sustainable Energy Action Plans in pilots to be carried out in Navarra (ES), Skåne (SW) and Emilia Romagna (IT). These regions represent different types of EU regions and will serve as samples to many others in which the learnings and best practices can be transferred.

PLAN4CET will be executed by a consortium composed by a group of 11 entities located in 4 European Countries (Spain, Sweden, Italy, and Belgium), involving different type local and regional public authorities together with other entities. This project proposal was presented in the 2021 call, being favourably evaluated and entering the reserve list. It was not finally financed due to budget unavailability.

Summary

Summary of Deliverable

The CET requires not only technology and investment but also **collaborative governance** that unites institutions, enterprises, associations, public administrations, and citizens. European municipalities and regions must balance ambitious climate neutrality goals with their diverse socio-demographic and territorial contexts.

One promising pathway is **inter-municipal cooperation**, which fosters dialogue among municipalities with similar socio-economic and energy profiles, enabling knowledge exchange, resource sharing, and more equitable transition processes.

A second dimension is the role of **Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)**. Beyond financing tools, PPPs function as hybrid alliances where municipalities, companies, research institutions, and civil society co-design strategies and pilot innovative projects. Evidence from workshops in Parma, Navarra, and Skåne highlights PPPs as platforms for experimentation, innovation, and legitimacy-building.

Finally, **Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)** demonstrate how governance materializes locally. As dynamic socio-technical processes, PEDs embody the **Quintuple Helix approach**, aligning European targets with local realities while fostering **collective ownership** of the transition.

Spelling Guidelines

Standardised British Spelling (NOT Oxford Spelling!) should be used in all documents. Generic terms are spelled in lower case, specific terms and proper names are spelled with initial capitals. For metric tonnes use the term “tonnes” and NOT tons.

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Abbreviation

CET – Clean Energy Transition

PPPs - Public-Private Partnerships

PEDs - Positive Energy Districts

SDGs - Sustainable Development Goal

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1. Introduction

The CET requires not only technological innovation and financial investment but also new forms of collaborative governance that bring together institutions, citizens, enterprises, associations, and public administrations. Across Europe, municipalities and regions face the dual challenge of implementing ambitious climate neutrality targets while managing their own socio-demographic and territorial specificities. Collaborative inter-municipal governance offers a promising pathway: by fostering dialogue and cooperation among municipalities with similar socio-economic, geographic, and energy characteristics, it enables the exchange of knowledge, resources, and best practices. Such alliances strengthen local capacities, reduce asymmetries between urban and rural contexts, and ensure that the transition is both inclusive and equitable.

This first part of the report “Collaborative inter-municipal governance” explores how socio-demographic characteristics of different case studies can influence and support governance processes, creating opportunities for cross-municipal learning and the sharing of best practices.

The second part, “Public–Private Partnerships in the Clean Energy Transition,” addresses the crucial role of Public–Private Partnerships (PPPs) as governance instruments for mobilizing financial resources, sharing risks, and co-producing innovative solutions. In the context of CET, PPPs go beyond contractual arrangements and take the form of hybrid alliances in which municipalities, companies, research institutions, and civil society co-design strategies and pilot transformative projects. Evidence gathered through the PLAN4CET workshop across the regions of Parma, Navarra, and Skåne shows that PPPs are not only financing mechanisms but also platforms for collaborative governance. They allow diverse actors to experiment, innovate, and build legitimacy, thereby accelerating the transition in ways that align public interests with private capabilities.

Finally, the third part focuses on Positive Energy Districts (PEDs), illustrating how the governance of CET materialises in practice. PEDs are not merely technical infrastructures but dynamic socio-technical processes that require the active participation of multiple stakeholders. Drawing on interviews conducted in the city of Parma, this section examines how institutions, enterprises, associations, citizens, and public administrations each play a distinct but interdependent role in co-imagining and co-creating these new urban ecosystems. PEDs demonstrate how the Quintuple Helix approach, integrating environmental, economic, political, social, and technological dimensions, can become a governance model that grounds ambitious European targets in local realities while fostering collective ownership of the transition.

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D2.2. Guide for stakeholder

2. Collaborative inter-municipal governance

J. Balest, C. Zandonella Callegher, F. Giussani

2.1. Introduction: strengthening local synergies for an inclusive climate and energy transition

In the face of intensifying climate change and evolving energy demands, European municipalities are increasingly called upon to act as frontline agents in the low-carbon transition. The European Green Deal places significant emphasis on the role of local and regional authorities in achieving its ambitious goals of climate neutrality and a sustainable society. Local governments are seen as crucial for translating the EU's overarching vision into concrete actions on the ground, engaging citizens and promoting concrete actions, which are context specific. However, while local administrations are uniquely positioned to translate European sustainability targets into place-based strategies, they often face challenges stemming from limited financial, technical, and human resources.

To overcome these constraints and accelerate the CET, fostering **collaborations and synergies among municipalities** - especially those with similar social, spatial, and energy characteristics - is both a strategic necessity and a powerful opportunity. Formal and informal collaborative governance structures that create collaborations between municipalities and other local and regional actors, propose benefits in achieving effective solutions, to common challenges.

As defined in the literature (e.g., in (Chapman et al., 2024), **collaborative governance** is a dynamic and iterative process aimed at achieving positive and equitable transformations in the urban environment—particularly through planning, designing, implementing, and managing common and public challenges. **Collaborative governance** refers to a (Chapman, Bukovszki, Van Lierop, Tomasi, & Pauleit, 2024) sector engage in joint decision-making and implementation processes **to pursue shared goals**. The concept acknowledges that governance extends beyond the formal actions of government alone, instead involving a network of institutions and non-state actors ((Healey, 2006; Holman, 2009) (Emerson, K., & Nabatchi, 2015). This shift recognizes the complexity of today's societal and climate change challenges, which cannot be effectively addressed by single actors operating in isolation.

The **advantages of collaborative governance** are manyfold. By involving diverse stakeholders in decision-making processes as well as proposing effective, strong, and cross-sectoral collaborations between and within public authorities, strategies and actions might be more legitimated. The case in which knowledge and resources are shared creates broader basis for effective and context-specific decisions, fostering innovation and adaptability, particularly important for complex, evolving challenges like climate change and energy transition. One more aspect that we can aim to is the advance of social equity in climate and energy transition processes. Cross-sectoral and cross-geographical collaborations between a diverse range of stakeholders, led by or with municipalities, can contribute to promote equity among territories that differ on the level of resources available (e.g., renewable sources, knowledge, developed areas).

Municipalities and local authorities play a pivotal role in enabling and shaping collaborative governance, particularly in the context of climate and energy transitions. As the closest tier of government to citizens and regional stakeholders, municipalities can act as key conveners, facilitators, and implementers. Their responsibilities include, for example, **creating enabling environments** for collaboration through policy frameworks, regulatory tools, and inclusive participatory processes. **Stewarding the public good**, municipalities can ensure that climate and energy strategies and actions contribute to social and environmental justice, **translating global and national climate goals** into locally relevant strategies and actions, grounded in community needs and capacities. **Mobilizing cross-sectoral partnerships** and fostering long-term, trust-based relationships among actors to co-create solutions, need many resources starting from knowledge and human capital, social capital and networking, as well as diverse territorial resources that differ among diverse geographies and populations. Summarizing, in advancing climate and energy transitions, collaborative governance allows municipalities to move beyond top-down planning approaches and instead co-develop systemic responses that are more context-sensitive, socially inclusive, and resilient.

We recognize the fundamental role of municipalities in climate and energy transition and we propose a tool to support the creation of knowledge to promote cross-territorial collaborative governance. Territories are not merely physical spaces but **sociotechnical systems**—interconnected networks of people, infrastructure, cultural practices, and energy flows. Recognizing this, recent research advocates for understanding municipalities not in isolation, but as part of broader **sociotechnical constellations** that evolve through shared dynamics and common potentials. This approach highlights that municipalities with similar demographic profiles, geographic settings, infrastructural assets, or energy priorities can benefit from **trans-local cooperation**, sharing not only resources and knowledge but also governance models, innovation pathways, and community engagement strategies.

Trans-local cooperation and **inter-municipal collaboration** becomes a key lever for:

- Scaling up renewable energy production
- Enhancing public acceptance and civic participation
- Integrating energy planning with risk management and spatial development
- Supporting vulnerable or isolated communities in accessing technical and financial resources

The case of South Tyrol demonstrates the power of this perspective. By identifying clusters of municipalities based on integrated social, energy, and spatial dimensions, Balest et al. (2019) illustrate how energy planning can be tailored to the specific characteristics of each group of municipalities, which share common features. More importantly, this approach shows that **planning at a trans-local scale**—beyond administrative borders and grounded in territorial cohesion—can enable more inclusive, efficient, and adaptive climate and energy action. Starting from the methodology developed in Balest et al. (2019), we explore the potential trans-local collaborations in other regions, namely Parma (IT) and Skane (SE).

The two regions are included in PLAN4CET project and need for support in developing and updating CET in a strategic manner. Based on the elaboration of clusters of similar municipalities, this report recommends cluster-specific roadmaps and shared strategies, aiming to turn local particularities into collective strength. By connecting municipalities not only geographically, but also **through shared challenges and capacities**, we can foster a more equitable and effective energy transition—one that is rooted in local realities but amplified through strategic collaboration—to be included in CET.

2.2. Methodology: building clusters with municipalities

This study adopts a data-driven methodology to identify groups of municipalities with similar socio-technical characteristics, with the aim of proposing trans-local collaboration and more effective energy planning at the local level. The approach is structured in three key phases:

1. Data selection and preparation: a set of 41 variables was selected, covering socio-demographic, socio-economic, cultural, spatial, infrastructural, energy, and governance dimensions.
2. Data preprocessing included cleaning, harmonization (especially for spatial datasets), and standardization to ensure comparability across variables.
3. Cluster analysis: a model-based clustering (Fraley & Raftery, 2002) approach was employed, utilizing parameterized finite Gaussian mixture models via the R package Mclust (Scrucca et al., 2023). The optimal number of clusters was determined based on the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) (Schwarz, 1978). To

achieve a comprehensive characterisation of the data, multiple clustering analyses were conducted. First, all indicators were considered simultaneously to obtain an overall, holistic clustering. Subsequently, separate analyses were performed individually on socio-economic, geographic, and energy-related indicators to explore domain-specific patterns. The quality of the resulting clusters was assessed by evaluating both their compactness and separation using both the Silhouette Score (Rousseeuw, 1987) and the Davies-Bouldin's Index (Davies & Bouldin, 1979). Finally, to support the interpretation of the identified clusters, Random Forest (Trevor, H., Tibshirani, R., & Friedman, 2009) classifiers were trained to determine the most important features distinguishing each group, based on feature importance scores.

The analysis focused on the two regions and identified n distinct clusters, each representing a unique sociotechnical system.

The current deliverable focuses on the pilot regions of Parma and Skåne, as these regions provided accessible, high-quality datasets that allowed for a complete application of the methodology. Navarra was not included at this stage due to practical data limitations: the official open-data portal (<https://gobiernoabierto.navarra.es/es/open-data>) was not operational during the analysis, preventing access to essential municipal datasets such as energy consumption, socio-economic indicators, and infrastructure information.

Including Navarra without these datasets would have required alternative data collection approaches, extensive harmonization efforts, and additional validation steps, which could have delayed the deliverable and compromised consistency across regions. By first applying the methodology in regions with complete data, we were able to ensure its robustness, test the analytical workflow, and refine the GIS-based clustering and interpretation approach.

Importantly, the methodology is fully designed to be transferable to Navarra once the necessary data are available. Applying the same rigorous process will allow for a consistent assessment of municipal clusters, identification of regional synergies, and formulation of tailored recommendations for renewable energy planning. The phased approach demonstrates both the replicability of the methodology and its adaptability to different regional contexts, ensuring that Navarra can be integrated seamlessly in future analyses without compromising analytical quality.

Mapping and Interpretation

Results were visualized using GIS tools to facilitate understanding and use by policymakers. Clusters were interpreted in terms of their renewable energy preferences, socio-economic context, geographic characteristics, and potential for collaboration. Based on the interpretation of clusters, a set of recommended actions are provided.

This methodology offers a replicable tool for regional administrations to identify commonalities among municipalities, supporting cooperative energy planning that is socially inclusive, spatially aware, and tailored to local needs.

2.3. Results: opportunities for inter-municipal collaboration

This section presents a qualitative overview and comparison of the different groups of municipalities, identified as clusters according to the methodology outlined below. These homogeneous clusters represent potential alliances of municipalities that could engage in strategic cooperation through joint initiatives or even shared CET. The proposed methodology identifies common characteristics and potential needs within each group, providing a foundation for cross-sectoral and cross-geographical strategic planning. The subsequent section illustrates the case of Parma (Italy) by analysing its placement within the identified clusters, while the following section applies the same clustering approach to the case of Skåne (Sweden), proposing opportunities for inter-municipal collaboration.

Parma (IT) and its potential alliances

Four distinct clusters - labelled A through D - have been identified, each characterized by a unique combination of geographical, socio-economic, and environmental features (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Results of the cluster analysis for the case study of Parma (Italy). NA indicates municipalities that were excluded from the analysis for missing data ($n = 1$) or because they were considered as outliers ($n = 1$). Source: own elaboration.

Cluster A is composed of municipalities located at higher elevations with a significant presence of forested areas, typically associated with lower *per capita* income levels. **Cluster B** includes municipalities facing strong hydrological risks but relatively low land-related risks. These areas tend to have very low forest coverage and lie at low elevations. Energy production in these municipalities is underdeveloped, particularly in terms of photovoltaic and biogas installations. **Cluster C** consists of more urbanized municipalities with larger populations and higher *per capita* incomes. Although these areas often have limited renewable energy penetration, some demonstrate relatively strong biogas production. Lastly, **Cluster D** includes municipalities with the highest exposure to land-related risks, such as mountainous terrain or flood-prone zones, and are generally among the least populated areas. Two municipalities, marked as 'NA', were excluded from the analysis. One was omitted due to missing data and the other, the municipality of Parma, was removed for being considered as an outlier. Given its higher level of urbanisation compared to the surrounding rural areas, Parma presents unique dynamics that would not be properly represented by the cluster analysis.

While this clustering offers a solid baseline for understanding potential synergies, it lacks the specificity required for defining targeted actions. To address this, we have developed

a refined clustering system based on a broader set of indicators, including socio-demographic variables, as detailed in the following sections.

Socio-demographic clusters

This clustering focuses on social and socio-economic indicators, including population size, aging and youth indexes, income *per capita*, and levels of political and associative participation. As shown in the corresponding map (see Figure 2), the geographical distribution of these clusters closely resembles the one identified in the previous section.

Figure 2: Results of the cluster analysis on socio-demographic indicators for Parma (Italy). "NA" marks municipalities excluded for missing data ($n = 1$) or outliers ($n = 1$). Source: own elaboration.

Cluster A comprises municipalities with smaller population size, lower *per capita* incomes, and notably high levels of associative participation. **Cluster B** includes areas with a relatively high number of young residents, but also a significant presence of elderly people, suggesting a possible gap in the middle-aged demographic. **Cluster C** consists of the most densely populated municipalities, marked by higher per capita income and strong political participation.

The socioeconomic potential to support the energy transition varies significantly across clusters. In **Cluster A**, the presence of active associations could serve as a valuable resource for community-driven initiatives, making associative networks a key lever for engagement. In **Cluster B**, tailored strategies could target both the elderly and younger

populations, mobilizing these groups through age-specific outreach and education. **Cluster C**, with its stronger institutional capacity and economic resources, may benefit from the active involvement of political bodies and greater potential for private investment in renewable energy initiatives.

Given these diverse characteristics, **a key question emerges:** how can municipalities leverage their specific social and socio-economic assets to foster broad public engagement in the energy transition?

Geographical clusters

The geographical clusters identified in this analysis show a distribution that closely mirrors the clustering presented earlier, which reinforces the validity of the approach and supports the development of more concrete and location-specific recommendations. This clustering is based on geographical characteristics such as total area, elevation, degree of urbanization, forest cover, and road surface coverage (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Results of the cluster analysis on geographical indicators for Parma (Italy). “NA” marks municipalities excluded for missing data ($n = 1$) or outliers ($n = 1$). Source: own elaboration.

Cluster A includes municipalities with larger surface areas and lower levels of urbanization, but with relatively low forest cover. These areas likely correspond to rural or mountainous regions. **Cluster B** represents the most urbanized municipalities, characterized by a dense

road network and compact spatial layout. **Cluster C** exhibits moderate values across the analyzed features, suggesting a composition of rural or peri-urban areas with a balanced mix of land uses.

These geographical distinctions have important implications for energy planning. Urban municipalities in **Cluster B** may be more suitable for technologies such as district heating networks or rooftop solar installations, given their density and infrastructure. In contrast, rural and peri-urban areas - represented by **Clusters A** and **C** - could benefit from leveraging local biomass resources or implementing small-scale hydroelectric systems, depending on local conditions and resource availability.

Given these diverse characteristics, **a key question emerges** also in this case: how can municipalities leverage their specific territorial resources (e.g., road surfaces, forest and biomass, urbanization) to push for energy transition?

Energy cluster

Although this clustering largely reproduces the geographical distribution observed in previous groupings, some notable differences emerge. This analysis specifically focuses on energy infrastructure and environmental risks, taking into account the presence of solar, geothermal, biomass, and PV installations, as well as exposure to hydro and land-related risks.

Cluster A is characterized by a significant presence of biomass energy plants and a medium to high level of land-related risk. **Cluster B** shows strong development in both biomass and PV energy infrastructure, while also experiencing medium to high land risk. **Cluster C**, on the other hand, faces high hydro-related risk but has limited energy infrastructure and an almost complete absence of PV installations.

All three clusters require risk mitigation strategies, with hydro risk being a priority for **Cluster C**, and land risk mitigation necessary for **Clusters A** and **B**. Additionally, investment in energy infrastructure remains a shared need across all clusters. Inter-cluster collaboration could play a key role in addressing these challenges, particularly through peer-to-peer knowledge exchange. For instance, municipalities in **Cluster B**, with more advanced experience in biomass energy development, could share insights on project implementation and investment processes, offering valuable guidance to others aiming to build similar capacity.

The question raised here is: Are there knowledge resources available to be shared within and between clusters of municipalities in order to increase competences on the diffusion of renewable energy plants?

Consensus cluster

This consensus clustering combines the previous three classifications - socio-demographic, geographical, and energy-related - into six integrated clusters, labelled **A** through **F** (see Figure 4). **Clusters A and B** are likely to represent rural or mountainous areas characterized by low-income levels and a limited presence of young people. These areas, however, show promising development in PV infrastructure and possess significant biomass potential due to forested landscapes. **Clusters C and E** correspond to more urbanized environments with moderate features, making them suitable as transitional zones for climate and energy policies. **Clusters D and F** are defined primarily by their high exposure to land-related risks and are likely to include rural or peripheral municipalities. Notably, **Cluster D** also exhibits low levels of political participation. While this final clustering scheme is more complex to interpret, its nuance allows for the design of targeted policies that align with each cluster’s specific capacities and potential.

Figure 4: Results of the cluster analysis for Parma (Italy), combining socio-demographic, geographical, and energy indicators. “NA” marks municipalities excluded for missing data (n = 1) or outliers (n = 1). Source: own elaboration.

Opportunities for cross-municipal collaboration and cluster-specific recommendations

Cluster B

Municipalities falling within **Cluster B** show notable development in biomass and PV

energy infrastructure yet remain exposed to medium to high levels of land-related risks. In the consensus clustering, these areas are likely rural or mountainous, characterized by low-income levels and a reduced presence of young residents. Given these attributes, municipalities in this cluster should prioritize the scaling-up of existing renewable energy systems, especially solar and biomass. Collaborative efforts to manage land-related risks would also be highly beneficial, including coordinated planning for erosion control, slope stabilization, and land-use zoning. Furthermore, to counter depopulation trends, local governments should promote the renovation and reuse of abandoned buildings, thereby enhancing both energy efficiency and community revitalization.

- ❖ Invest in scaling up solar and biomass infrastructure
- ❖ Elaborate shared actions for land risk management
- ❖ Combats depopulation by promoting the renovation of existing and abandoned buildings

Cluster C

Cluster C encompasses urbanized municipalities that are economically more prosperous, politically engaged, and densely populated. These areas represent fertile ground for individual and collective energy transition initiatives. Municipalities in this cluster should actively involve citizens in participatory planning processes and educational campaigns to build awareness and foster ownership. Financial incentives - such as subsidies for energy retrofitting and renewable energy installations - —can play a critical role in encouraging household-level action. Moreover, given their density, these municipalities are well-positioned to develop district heating networks and to implement building-level mandates for photovoltaic systems and energy efficiency standards. The integration of green infrastructure is also essential to mitigate the urban heat island effect and improve overall climate resilience.

- ❖ Develop educational campaigns and participatory planning to engage citizens
- ❖ Provide financial incentives or subsidies for energy efficiency retrofits and installations of individual renewable energy plants
- ❖ Foster local energy cooperatives to empower civic participation
- ❖ Capitalize on urban density for district heating networks
- ❖ Incorporate green infrastructure to combat heat island effects
- ❖ Promote building-level PV installations and energy efficiency mandates

Clusters D and F

Clusters D and **F** are identified as high-risk areas, particularly vulnerable to land-related hazards. They are generally rural or peripheral in nature, with **Cluster D** additionally characterized by low levels of political participation. Municipalities in these clusters should

prioritize climate adaptation through investments in flood control infrastructure, soil stabilization measures, and early warning systems. Given the potential limitations in grid access, off-grid and microgrid renewable energy solutions may offer viable pathways for local energy security. In parallel, it is crucial to actively pursue national and EU-level funding schemes to compensate for local resource constraints and to support the development of resilient infrastructure.

- ❖ Prioritize climate adaptation: flood control, soil stabilization, early warning systems
- ❖ Invest in off-grid or microgrid renewable solutions
- ❖ Target national or EU funding schemes to offset local resource limitations

Cluster A

Cluster A includes municipalities with extensive land areas, typically rural or mountainous, that demonstrate medium to high exposure to land-related risks. While forest cover is relatively low overall, biomass energy installations are notably present. These municipalities should prioritize climate adaptation actions similar to those proposed for **Clusters D** and **F**, focusing on preventive infrastructure and land risk mitigation. In addition, effective forest resource management can provide dual benefits—enhancing energy production through sustainable biomass while simultaneously reducing the vulnerability to land degradation and natural hazards.

- ❖ Prioritize climate adaptation: flood control, soil stabilization, early warning systems
- ❖ Management of forest resources can be positive for both energy production and land risk management

Cross-cutting actions

While the above actions are tailored to specific cluster profiles, broader strategies should be pursued across all municipalities. A more targeted and customized approach could be developed through deeper engagement with individual municipalities or well-defined subgroups, supported by technical assistance and alliance-building. Municipalities are encouraged to establish inter-cluster collaboration platforms to facilitate the exchange of best practices, operational experiences, and technical know-how. Governance models should be designed to accommodate the diversity of cluster profiles, allowing flexibility for municipalities to adopt adaptive and context-specific CET. In addition, integrated planning that links energy strategies with land-use policies is essential, particularly in areas with complex geographical features and overlapping risks. Both intra-cluster (among municipalities with similar characteristics) and inter-cluster (across different profiles) cooperation should be promoted. This approach will allow municipalities to pool resources, harmonize efforts, address shared challenges, and drive a more inclusive and just energy transition. Actions are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. List of cluster specific recommendation and cross-cutting actions involving municipalities from different clusters.

Theme	Intra-cluster example	Inter-clusters example
Knowledge exchange	Municipalities in Energy Cluster B share lessons and strategies on PV/biomass development	Energy Cluster C (limited infrastructure) learns from B's successful projects
Resource complementarity	Consensus clusters A/B share forest/biomass planning strategies	Geo cluster A (rural biomass-rich) teams with geo clusters B and C (more urbanized) to supply district heating or biomass
Climate risk management	Energy cluster C focuses on hydro risk management	Energy cluster B (land risk) and cluster A (land risk) co-develop joint early-warning and adaptation systems
Civic engagement	Socio cluster A shares its associative network strategies. Socio cluster C shares methods for engaging politically active citizens	All three clusters share know-how on how to activate citizens in the energy transition and risk management.
Funding access	Consensus cluster C/E collaborates for accessing for funding, sharing the important resources that can make the request successful	Consensus cluster D/F (low capacity) applies jointly with cluster C/E (high capacity)
Policy alignment	Policy alignment withing cluster energy A to face land risks	Cross-cluster alignment for region-wide energy/risk management risk strategy (e.g., cluster energy A + B)

Thematic overview of collaboration opportunities

To illustrate the benefits of collaboration, the following examples demonstrate how intra- and inter-cluster cooperation can be activated across key themes:

- **Knowledge exchange and capacity building:** municipalities in **Cluster B** (energy) can share their experience with PV and biomass systems with **Cluster C**, where infrastructure is less developed. Similarly, urban municipalities in **Cluster B** (geographical) can support rural areas (**Clusters A** and **C**) with institutional knowledge and technical expertise.

- **Resource complementarity:** **Clusters A and B** (consensus) can coordinate forest and biomass resource strategies, while rural, biomass-rich municipalities in **Cluster A** can partner with more urbanized **Clusters B and C** to develop shared heating solutions or biomass supply chains.
- **Climate risk management:** **Cluster C** (energy), which is exposed to hydro-related risks, can develop tailored flood response strategies, while municipalities in **Clusters A and B** (energy) facing land risks can collaborate on joint adaptation planning, such as early warning systems or slope stabilization projects.
- **Civic engagement:** **Cluster A** (socio) can offer models for mobilizing community associations, whereas **Cluster C** can provide insights into leveraging political participation for energy transition. Knowledge-sharing among all clusters can strengthen citizen involvement in climate and energy initiatives.
- **Funding access:** urbanized and resource-rich municipalities in **Clusters C and E** (consensus) can lead joint funding applications and provide administrative support to smaller, resource-constrained areas in **Clusters D and F**.
- **Policy alignment:** **Cluster A** (energy) could align policies internally to better manage land-related risks, while multi-cluster cooperation could lead to region-wide strategies integrating energy development with risk mitigation.

Cluster-based recommendations for Climate and Energy Transition Planning in Skane

This chapter presents an analysis of the clusters identified in the Sweden case study, offering recommendations for intra-cluster collaboration and cluster-specific strategies. By grouping municipalities with shared socio-economic, geographic, and energy characteristics, we can tailor CET more effectively and identify synergies for cooperation and shared learning.

Overview of clustering results

The analysis includes five cluster configurations:

- Cluster all: combined variables (excluding forest and road coverage)
- Cluster socio: based on socio-economic indicators
- Cluster geo: based on geographic characteristics
- Cluster energy: based on renewable energy potentials
- Cluster consensus: a composite of social, geo, and energy clusters

The consensus clustering, which integrates multiple dimensions, provides the most comprehensive typology and forms the basis of our recommendations.

This cluster-based approach enables municipalities to build targeted, context-specific CET while benefiting from shared knowledge and joint action. By aligning on common challenges and leveraging complementary strengths, Swedish municipalities can accelerate their energy transitions more efficiently and equitably. However, the number of

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municipalities is low compared to the numerosity needed for a cluster analysis. Therefore, we propose to focus on clusters based on energy features in the following section.

Energy cluster

Figure 5: Results of the cluster analysis on the energy indicators for the case study of Skåne (Sweden) combining the results of socio-demographic, geographical, and energy clusters. Source: own elaboration.

As illustrated in the map, the municipalities can be grouped into three distinct clusters based on their renewable energy characteristics. **Cluster C** stands out for its relatively high share of surface dedicated to solar energy production and a notable presence of geothermal power plants. However, despite its strengths in these areas, it shows a lower rate of PV installations compared to the other clusters. On the other hand, **Clusters A and B** - although currently less developed in terms of solar surface utilization or geothermal infrastructure - show significant potential to become frontrunners in expanding PV deployment.

In light of these findings, strategic cooperation among the clusters could accelerate renewable energy development more evenly across the region. One recommended pathway is the establishment of inter-cluster capacity-building initiatives, where municipalities can share expertise, tools, and best practices related to stakeholder engagement, accessing funding mechanisms, and applying climate modelling tools. For instance, municipalities in **Cluster C**, with more experience in geothermal and solar surface planning, could support **Clusters A and B** in strengthening their technical and institutional capacities in the case they share similar renewable energy potential.

Moreover, a coordinated approach to policy advocacy would be beneficial. By forming a unified voice, municipalities from different clusters could present joint recommendations to national authorities, advocating for enhanced funding mechanisms, streamlined regulatory procedures, and broader support for community-led renewable energy

initiatives. A shared strategy would increase the visibility and impact of their demands, aligning local needs with national and European climate goals.

Table 2: Summary of key recommendations

Recommendation area	Description
Common capacity-building	Establish inter-cluster knowledge exchanges and joint training on PV/geothermal installation, stakeholder engagement, and climate modelling.
Joint policy advocacy	Collaborate on shared policy proposals to national bodies, focusing on better funding access and regulatory support for renewables.
Shared efforts towards common plans	Collaborate to define and design common Climate and Energy Transition Plans, sharing resources and objectives.

2.4. Conclusions

This chapter presents two applications of a methodological approach designed to identify potential alliances among municipalities. The goal is to foster more effective responses to shared challenges and needs by encouraging resource sharing while respecting local and regional specificities. Through a clustering analysis based on a range of indicators - including population dynamics, territorial characteristics, energy infrastructure, and climate risk exposure - the chapter outlines groupings of municipalities with similar profiles and priorities. For each cluster, corresponding action proposals have been developed to support joint planning and implementation.

This methodology could support the **co-creation of alliances** to be included in CET. The information included in this report is intended to serve as a basis for dialogues between municipalities aimed to defining common priorities, objectives, and actions. The importance of creating collaborations and alliances in the CET lies in their potential to enhance and increase the resources available for this transition—especially in a sector where the public sector often faces limited human, technical, and financial resources. Therefore, the results of this report alone can provide only a **general and partial overview** based on the data collected and the specific characteristics of the territories. Nonetheless, the results presented can serve as an important foundation for co-creation processes in which municipalities and local authorities play a central role in defining concrete and effective actions.

In conclusion, the findings highlight significant opportunities emerging from this methodology. While the chapter outlines a set of general recommendations, the approach also lends itself to more tailored services. Customized consultancy can be offered to individual municipalities or targeted groups to support the development of CET through the formation of strategic alliances. This method thus serves as both a planning tool and a framework for collaboration, enabling more adaptive and locally grounded climate and energy strategies.

3. Public-Private Partnership in the Clean Energy Transition

F. Voltolini

The global shift toward clean energy represents one of the most profound transformations of the 21st century. Governments worldwide have committed to ambitious decarbonization targets in line with the Paris Agreement and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and at European level the European Green Deal. Achieving these objectives requires unprecedented investment in renewable energy generation, grid modernization, energy efficiency, storage technologies, and emerging solutions. Estimates from international agencies, including the United Nations, suggest that trillions of dollars in new infrastructure investment will be needed annually to meet net-zero targets by mid-century. Public resources alone are insufficient to finance this transition, and private sector participation is indispensable. In recognition of this, governments at COP29 in November 2024 agreed to establish a New Collective Quantified Goal on climate finance of at least \$300 billion per year by 2035—tripling the previously agreed target—and to mobilize efforts across public and private entities to scale up finance for developing countries to \$1.3 trillion per year by 2035.

At the same time, climate adaptation is becoming increasingly costly as the magnitude of climate change sets in. The United Nations Environment Programme estimates that countries may need to spend up to \$387 billion annually by 2030, and significantly more by 2050. Yet despite these growing needs—and pledges made at COP26 in Glasgow to double adaptation finance to around \$40 billion per year by 2025—adaptation finance reached only \$32.4 billion in 2022. Current flows of international public adaptation finance remain 10 to 18 times lower than what is required, underscoring the urgent gap between commitments and implementation.

PPPs have emerged as a vital mechanism for mobilizing private capital, sharing risks, and leveraging innovation to accelerate the CET (Casadey et al. 2024). A PPP broadly refers to a contractual arrangement between public authorities and private entities for the delivery of infrastructure or services that traditionally fall within the public sector's mandate. In the energy context, PPPs enable governments to attract investment for renewable power plants, grid expansion, energy storage facilities, electric mobility infrastructure, and other clean technologies, while ensuring that projects align with international and national climate policies and public interests.

The relevance of PPPs lies not only in closing financing gaps but also in enhancing project bankability, transferring technical expertise, and fostering long-term operational efficiency.

By balancing public oversight with private sector innovation and efficiency, PPPs can unlock scalable solutions for decarbonization. At the same time, their design requires careful attention to regulatory frameworks, risk allocation, and stakeholder engagement to ensure projects are socially equitable, environmentally sustainable, and replicable across different contexts.

This chapter explores the role of PPPs in advancing the CET. The aim is to provide policymakers, investors, and practitioners with a grounded understanding of how PPPs can serve as a bridge between public climate commitments and private sector capacity, ultimately accelerating the path toward a low-carbon future.

It draws on review of scientific and non - scientific documents as well as insights gathered during a workshop with the partners of the PLAN4CET project, who shared their experiences and perspectives on PPPs in the clean energy sector. By combining academic evidence with practical experience from stakeholders directly engaged in the transition, the chapter examines the rationale for PPPs, reviews different models and case studies, highlights barriers and challenges, and outlines enabling policy frameworks.

3.1. PPP: definitions form the literature

To better understand the state of knowledge on the role of PPPs in the clean energy transition, we conducted a review of both scientific and non-scientific publications. The aim is to provide policymakers, investors, and practitioners with a grounded understanding of how PPPs can serve as a bridge between public climate commitments and private sector capacity, ultimately accelerating the path toward a low-carbon future. The review also aimed to place PPPs within the broader governance and financing debate around renewable energy and low-carbon infrastructure, where the need for mobilizing private investment alongside public resources is particularly urgent.

A widely used definition of PPPs was formulated in 2004 by the European Commission in its Green Paper on Public-Private Partnerships (European Commission, 2004). The document describes PPPs as “forms of cooperation between public authorities and the world of business which aim to ensure the funding, construction, renovation, management or maintenance of an infrastructure or the provision of a service.” This characterization highlights PPPs as long-term collaborative arrangements in which public authorities and private operators work together across different stages of a project.

According to the Green Paper, several elements normally characterize PPPs:

1. they are relatively long-term in duration, often extending across the life cycle of a project from design to implementation and operation;

2. funding typically comes in part from the private sector, often through complex financial structures, but public contributions may also be significant;
3. the private partner plays an important role in project design, financing, and implementation, while the public partner concentrates on defining objectives in terms of public interest, service quality, and pricing policies, and takes responsibility for monitoring compliance;
4. the distribution of risks: while risks traditionally borne by the public sector are transferred to the private partner, PPPs do not necessarily imply that the latter assumes all risks. Instead, the allocation is determined case by case, depending on the ability of each party to manage particular risks effectively;

The World Bank offers a complementary perspective, defining a PPP as a long-term contractual partnership between a government entity and a private party, in which the latter is responsible for delivering a public asset or service while assuming substantial project-related risks in financing, construction, or operation (World Bank, 2024). Once again, the emphasis is placed on risk allocation and on the ability of private actors to contribute not only financial resources, but also expertise and efficiency (World Bank, 2024).

From a historical perspective, PPPs began to take shape in the early 1990s as a distinctive form of public procurement designed to link governments with the business sector. Initially, PPPs were seen mainly as contractual tools for mobilizing private finance in public infrastructure projects. Over time, however, they evolved into more complex and sophisticated governance mechanisms that combine financial innovation, regulatory oversight, and stakeholder cooperation. Scholars such as Casady et al. (2020) and Hodge and Greve (2010) emphasize that PPPs have expanded beyond simple procurement models to become broader arrangements for the joint delivery and operation of infrastructure and services.

At the same time, the term PPP has been applied in a broader sense to describe less formal or structured partnerships between the public and private sectors. Osborne and Murray (2000) and Bjärstig (2017) argue that the concept also encompasses ad hoc collaborations and special partnership initiatives that may not rely on formal contracts but still embody joint public-private engagement in the pursuit of shared goals. This wider conceptualization underscores the diversity of PPPs, ranging from formalized legal frameworks to more flexible and adaptive forms of cooperation.

A consistent theme in the literature is the distinction between PPPs and traditional public procurement. In a conventional procurement process, the public administration defines the methods and specifications of the project in detail, and then delegates execution to a

private contractor. The private operator's role is limited to fulfilling the technical requirements set by the administration, with relatively little autonomy in shaping the project outcomes (Forrer et al., 2010).

By contrast, PPPs entail a deeper form of collaboration. The public and private actors jointly define not only the objectives but also the modalities through which those objectives will be achieved. This joint responsibility gives the private operator greater involvement in design, financing, and implementation, but also entails assuming greater risks. The fundamental difference lies in the degree of partnership: while traditional procurement is transactional, PPPs are relational, embedding risk-sharing and long-term cooperation into the governance of infrastructure and services.

3.2. PPP in the Clean Energy Transition

The above described definitional and conceptual insights are particularly relevant when examining PPPs in the context of the CET. Renewable energy projects, grid expansion, energy efficiency measures, and emerging technologies often require substantial upfront investment, long development horizons, and exposure to technological and market risks. PPPs provide a mechanism for combining public oversight—focused on climate targets, service quality, and equity—with private sector efficiency, technical expertise, and financial capacity.

The literature suggests that PPPs can help close the financing gap in renewable energy by mobilizing private capital, reducing pressure on public budgets, and creating bankable projects through risk-sharing arrangements (Casady et al., 2020). At the same time, their success depends heavily on robust institutional frameworks, transparent procurement, and well-designed contracts that balance public interests with private incentives. Without these conditions, PPPs risk generating inefficiencies or inequities, such as cost overruns, high tariffs, or imbalanced risk allocation.

3.3. Insights from the Workshop

Within the PLAN4CET project, an in-person workshop was conducted to gather empirical experience on the development and implementation of PPPs in the pilot regions of Skåne (Sweden), Pamplona (Spain), and Parma (Italy). The workshop was held during the project meeting in Helsingborg (Sweden) at the beginning of April 2025. Participants were organized into three discussion groups, deliberately composed to include representatives from different regions, thereby facilitating cross-regional knowledge exchange. The workshop was structured in two sequential phases. In the first phase, each participant completed an individual form, providing an example of a PPP in the context of the clean

energy transition, including a description of the actors involved and the specific activities undertaken within the partnership.

In the second phase, the participants discussed within their own groups in a structured session aimed at analysing and comparing the selected PPPs, with particular attention to the challenges and opportunities related to the relational aspect of cooperation, stakeholder engagement strategies to involve participants, and methods to collect contribution and ideas observed across the different cases. This approach allowed the project to systematically capture both individual experiences and collective insights on PPP governance and implementation in diverse regional contexts.

3.4. Methodology and Insights

The first phase of the PLAN4CET workshop was designed to gather individual experiences and perceptions of PPPs in the CET across the three pilot regions (Skåne in Sweden, Pamplona in Spain, and Parma in Italy). Each participant was asked to complete a structured form providing:

1. An example of a clean energy transition (CET) collaboration they were familiar with;
2. A description of the actors involved;
3. An explanation of how collaboration was organized and managed.

This exercise aimed to capture both the diversity of PPP arrangements in the energy transition and the specific roles of stakeholders in their implementation.

Examples of CET Collaborations

The examples collected revealed a wide range of PPP applications in the clean energy sector, from financing mechanisms to energy infrastructure projects. For instance, participants from Pamplona emphasized collaborations between local government, business, and citizens to facilitate CET activities, while those from Parma highlighted municipal partnerships with technology providers and housing cooperatives. In Skåne, examples included regional-scale collaborations with research institutions and energy companies, often framed around pilot projects in renewable energy and mobility.

Despite the diversity of cases, common themes emerged. First, most PPPs were established with the objective of pooling resources and expertise to overcome financial and technical barriers. Second, partnerships were often motivated by the need to foster legitimacy and broad stakeholder engagement, especially where citizen participation was required to ensure the adoption of renewable energy solutions.

Box 1 – The case of Elmer 2.0 in Skåne

The ELmer 2.0 project can be described as a PPP that illustrates how collaborative governance mechanisms are mobilized to address energy system challenges at the regional level. In line with the European Commission’s Green Paper definition, ELmer 2.0 constitutes a long-term cooperative arrangement between public authorities—represented by Region Skåne and the participating municipalities— and private sector actors, including local distribution companies such as E.ON and C4 Energi. The project is not limited to contractual service delivery but instead involves joint planning, scenario development, and strategic dialogue, thereby embodying the broader conceptualization of PPPs as multi-actor collaborations aimed at delivering complex public goods.

From a financial perspective, ELmer 2.0 combines public and private resources in ways that reflect the hybrid funding structures typical of PPPs. The Swedish Energy Agency provides the main financial support, while utilities and municipalities contribute expertise, data, and in-kind resources. This blending of funding and competences allows the project to undertake activities that neither the public nor the private sector could efficiently achieve alone, such as localized energy modelling and cross-sectoral stakeholder engagement.

The role of the private sector within ELmer 2.0 is particularly significant. Companies such as E.ON and C4 Energi are not merely service providers but active participants in planning and forecasting exercises. Their technical knowledge and operational perspectives ensure that the scenarios and strategies developed are both realistic and implementable. Public actors, by contrast, retain responsibility for defining objectives in the public interest—such as ensuring security of supply, enabling economic growth, and supporting the green transition—while also monitoring project outcomes. This division of roles aligns with the governance dynamics of PPPs, where public authorities set goals and regulatory frameworks, and private actors contribute technical solutions and operational expertise.

ELmer 2.0 exemplifies how PPPs in the CET extend beyond traditional procurement models. Rather than focusing solely on construction or service delivery, the project highlights the importance of knowledge co-production, integrated planning, and multi-level governance.

Actors Involved in the Partnerships

The analysis of the individual responses in the template shows that PPPs in the CET typically involve a broad constellation of stakeholders. Public authorities (regional governments, municipalities) consistently played a central role in defining objectives and providing institutional legitimacy. Private actors ranged from energy utilities, banks, and technology providers to enterprises. Civil society actors, particularly citizens and associations, were also frequently included, reflecting the importance of participatory governance in CET projects.

Interestingly, the workshop data indicate that the financial sector—especially banks—was perceived as an essential but sometimes underrepresented partner. Their involvement was often linked to the ability to scale up projects and secure long-term sustainability. Research institutions and universities also appeared as key knowledge providers, bridging the gap between policy, innovation, and practice.

Box 2 - Parma Carbon Neutrality Territorial Alliancer

The Parma Carbon Neutrality Territorial Alliance is an innovative form of PPP designed to support the decarbonization of the province of Parma by 2030. Although not structured as a classical contractual PPP, it reflects the essential features identified in the European Commission's Green Paper: long-term cooperation, hybrid resource mobilization, significant involvement of private actors, and differentiated risk-sharing.

The initiative brings together public authorities - most prominently the Municipality and Province of Parma and regional institutions - with private actors from agriculture, industry, services, and utilities, as well as civil society organizations and cultural institutions. This wide spectrum of participants illustrates the PPP principle of linking government with the business sector while also expanding it to encompass broader societal engagement.

The funding and resource model combines public financial support with private contributions in the form of knowledge, technical expertise, organizational capacity, and citizen-led initiatives. Such resources is consistent with the PPP logic of combining public oversight with private innovation and investment capacity. Private actors are not passive beneficiaries but are deeply involved in co-defining strategies, piloting new solutions, and providing sector-specific insights.

Risk-sharing within the Alliance operates primarily in governance and reputational terms rather than financial ones. The uncertainty of achieving carbon neutrality by 2030, given Parma's above-average per capita CO₂ emissions, represents a collective

risk. Public institutions assume responsibility for policy coherence, strategic planning, and monitoring, while private and civil society actors contribute through experimentation, implementation of decarbonization practices, and technological adoption. The shared responsibility for both successes and potential shortcomings mirrors the adaptive, case-by-case allocation of risks described in the Green Paper.

In sum, the Parma Carbon Neutrality Alliance is an example of a PPP oriented toward societal transformation rather than infrastructure provision. Its defining features—long-term orientation, hybrid funding and resource structures, substantial private sector and civil society involvement, and collaborative risk-sharing—situate it firmly within the PPP framework, while also extending it into new domains of climate governance. This case highlights how PPPs in the CET can transcend traditional project-based models and instead operate as broad territorial alliances mobilizing multiple forms of capital—financial, social, and institutional—to achieve ambitious climate objectives.

Modes of Collaboration

Participants described a variety of mechanisms through which these partnerships operated. Common methods included regular meetings, workshops, and structured dialogues with stakeholders. In several cases, digital tools (online meetings and platforms) complemented in-person collaboration, particularly during the design and monitoring phases.

Collaboration was not only technical but also relational: many responses highlighted the importance of trust-building, iterative dialogue, and the co-definition of goals. In some cases, collaboration took the form of highly formalized structures with contracts and governance boards; in others, it relied on more informal, ad hoc exchanges. This reflects the dual nature of PPPs as both formal procurement tools and flexible governance arrangements.

Box 3 – a case study in Navarra

SustaiNAVility, implemented between 2018 and 2021, exemplifies a multifaceted Public-Private Partnership (PPP) orchestrated to advance regional energy efficiency, renewable energy uptake, and carbon reduction across the Navarra region. Although not framed as a classical infrastructure PPP, its structure and governance embody

critical PPP dimensions: sustained collaboration, hybrid resourcing, active private-sector engagement, and nuanced risk distribution.

At the foundation of SustaiNAVility lies the coordinated leadership of the Government of Navarra (Comunidad Foral de Navarra), with Nasuvinsa, the public housing and urban development agency, serving as a central implementing partner. Collaboration extends to technical and consultancy partners such as the National Renewable Energy Centre (CENER), the Navarra Industry Association (AIN), and Zabala Innovation Consulting, reflecting the PPP principle of embedding public oversight alongside private-sector capabilities.

Funding for the initiative was provided through a grant of approximately €1.08 million under the European Horizon 2020 programme, with the explicit objective of catalyzing regional investments in energy efficiency and renewable energy totaling over €16 million. By the project's conclusion, the initiative had indeed accelerated €21.5 million in investments across public buildings, social and private housing, industry, street lighting, and electric mobility—evidencing substantial leveraging of public funds to mobilize broader capital flows.

Private and public actors were deeply involved throughout planning and implementation. Municipalities and public entities initiated efficiency measures in lighting and buildings, while citizens and businesses participated in energy renovations and behaviour change interventions. Nasuvinsa played a dual role: facilitating technical coordination and executing rehabilitation projects—effectively bridging public objectives with operational delivery. This echoes the PPP model where the private side contributes operational and technical expertise in service of public interest goals.

Risk-sharing in SustaiNAVility pertains to resource allocation, implementation uncertainty, and behavioural change rather than financial risk. The project addressed energy poverty, energy consumption variability, and investment challenges through shared ownership of outcomes. Public authorities assumed strategic direction and oversight, while private technical partners and citizens participated in delivering upgrades and engaging in energy-saving actions—distributing responsibility according to capacity and role.

The project's impact reinforces the adequacy of the PPP framing. SustainAVility achieved annual primary energy savings of approximately 38.18 GWh, supported the deployment of renewables, and made progress in reducing CO₂ emissions—substantive outcomes indicative of effective collaborative governance.

In sum, SustainAVility demonstrates how a PPP can be structured around policy delivery in the CET: long-term stakeholder collaboration, hybrid financial and technical resourcing, shared implementation across public and private entities, and collective handling of performance and behavioural risks. Though not a concession-based model, the project aligns closely with the broader, governance-oriented conceptualization of PPPs.

3.4.1. Second phase

The second phase of the PLAN4CET workshop was designed to collectively reflect on the strengths, weaknesses, and methods of engagement characterizing PPPs in the CET. Participants, were asked to discuss the perceived limits, the opportunities, and the engagement strategies that emerge in the design and implementation of PPPs in this field.

3.4.1.1. Limits and Challenges

Across the three regional contexts, participants identified a set of recurrent limitations that often hinder the effectiveness of PPPs in the CET. A first concern relates to the instability of participation, with actors frequently changing over the course of a project. This instability is compounded by a lack of technical expertise in specific domains, which constrains the capacity of both public and private partners to address complex infrastructural and energy challenges. Moreover, participants emphasized the difficulty of maintaining continuity in political support, as changes in government or administrative leadership may disrupt long-term initiatives. A final recurring theme concerned the scarcity of resources, both financial and human, which can limit the scale and ambition of collaborative efforts.

3.4.1.2. Opportunities

Despite these constraints, participants highlighted a variety of opportunities that PPPs can unlock when effectively structured. One important opportunity lies in the capacity of partnerships to mobilize additional financial resources, which are essential for enabling new clean energy projects. Equally, PPPs were seen as providing a platform to share risks and responsibilities, distributing them more equitably between public authorities and private actors, thus lowering the burden on individual stakeholders. Another important

dimension is the ability of PPPs to generate trust and legitimacy, especially when diverse actors - including municipalities, businesses, and citizens- are engaged in co-decision processes. This inclusiveness strengthens the perception of PPPs as win-win mechanisms that align public objectives with private incentives. Finally, participants underlined the role of PPPs in fostering innovation and experimentation, particularly when collaborations bring together actors from different sectors who would not otherwise interact.

3.4.1.3. Engagement Methods

The discussions also provided valuable insights into the mechanisms through which stakeholders can be engaged in PPPs. Face-to-face interactions- such as regular meetings, workshops, and site visits - were consistently highlighted as critical for building trust, fostering dialogue, and enabling mutual understanding of constraints and goals. Another important point that emerged was the value of creating informal opportunities for interaction, which can help cultivate a climate of trust and ensure that participation does not remain limited to the same group of stakeholders. In addition, online platforms and digital tools were recognized as valuable instruments for ensuring continuity of communication, particularly when actors are geographically dispersed. Several groups stressed the need for flexible and adaptive engagement methods, able to respond to changing circumstances, evolving project requirements, and the diverse interests of stakeholders. Importantly, participants noted that the success of engagement strategies depends not only on the frequency of interaction but also on the clarity of roles and responsibilities within the partnership.

3.5. Conclusion

The PLAN4CET workshop has provided valuable empirical insights into the ways in which Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) are designed, implemented, and perceived within the CET across the pilot regions of Skåne, Pamplona, and Parma. The individual case studies demonstrated that PPPs in this field extend well beyond traditional contractual arrangements. They instead represent hybrid governance mechanisms where public institutions, private companies, and civil society actors collaborate through diverse forms of resource mobilization, risk-sharing, and knowledge co-production. The cases of Elmer 2.0, the Parma Carbon Neutrality Territorial Alliance, and SustaiNAVility in Navarra highlight different models of partnership, yet all illustrate the essential PPP features of long-term cooperation, joint problem-solving, and the alignment of public and private interests toward sustainability objectives.

At the collective level, participants emphasized that PPPs face notable challenges, particularly in terms of resource constraints, the instability of participation, and the difficulty of sustaining political and technical continuity over time. Nonetheless, the

discussions underscored that these arrangements also offer substantial opportunities. PPPs enable financial leveraging, foster innovation, enhance legitimacy, and provide platforms for inclusive stakeholder engagement. The methods of collaboration identified—from formal governance structures to more informal, adaptive exchanges—further illustrate that successful PPPs rely on both technical coordination and relational trust-building.

Findings suggest that PPPs are a critical yet complex governance instrument for advancing the CET. Their effectiveness depends on the careful balancing of public oversight and private initiative, the inclusion of diverse stakeholders, and the establishment of flexible engagement mechanisms capable of adapting to evolving challenges. While limitations remain significant, the opportunities and added value highlighted in the workshop point to the transformative potential of PPPs as vehicles for delivering sustainable, long-term energy transitions across different regional contexts.

4. Collaborative governance, new emerging actors, and power dynamics

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The road to climate neutrality is not solely paved with technological innovations and strategic planning. As the PLAN4CET project highlights, the **governance dimension** - particularly in the public sector - is crucial to enabling sustainable, inclusive, and effective CET. Cities and regions, which account for the majority of energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, are increasingly positioned at the forefront of climate policy. Yet, translating high-level objectives into local action remains a complex task that demands rethinking traditional governance approaches (Dodman et al. 2023; (Bulkeley & Newell, 2010).

To address the multifaceted challenges of CET, a growing number of European municipalities and regions are adopting **collaborative governance** models. These approaches move beyond the hierarchical top-down paradigm, embracing horizontal and network-based coordination across sectors, jurisdictions, and **actors** (Zhou & Dai, 2023). **Collaborative governance** is considered as a process where public agencies engage with non-state actors in collective decision-making, sharing authority, resources, and responsibilities (Emerson et al., 2012).

Such models are particularly relevant for **small and medium-sized municipalities** - central to PLAN4CET's mission - which often lack the institutional capacity and technical know-how to act independently. Through collaboration, these municipalities can access external, context-sensitive resources and knowledge (Zhou & Dai, 2023).

Building on this foundation, Voets et al. (2021) offer a more refined and practice-oriented definition of collaborative governance as *"governing arrangements in which public and private actors collectively engage in decision-making and implementation processes to solve shared problems"* (p. 3). Their perspective underscores the **relational and dynamic nature of collaboration**: rather than being a fixed institutional arrangement, collaborative governance is a **process of negotiation, trust-building, and coordination**, often across organizational and sectoral boundaries. Importantly, it also provides a framework for **mutual learning and cross-contextual exchange**, enabling actors to **learn from the experiences of other regions, institutions, or sectors**, and to adapt solutions to their specific contexts. This dimension of learning is particularly relevant to the **PLAN4CET** project, which explicitly aims to foster **exchange and dialogue among municipalities and regions**, recognising that many of the barriers to CET are **shared across local contexts**. By encouraging the **sharing of experiences, tools, and practices**, the project seeks to

create a collaborative environment in which local and regional authorities can **co-develop solutions** to common challenges and accelerate progress through **collective learning**.

(Voets et al., 2021) also draw attention to the **preconditions for effective collaboration**, such as clearly defined roles, mutual understanding, leadership, and symmetrical power relations. Without these enabling factors, collaborative initiatives risk remaining symbolic or may reinforce existing power asymmetries. In particular, their work highlights that collaboration is not inherently democratic or effective - it must be **carefully designed and actively maintained** through continuous interaction and adaptive governance mechanisms.

Within the CET domain, this conceptualization is particularly useful: it reinforces the idea that successful transitions require **structured, transparent, and inclusive governance processes** capable of managing conflict, aligning diverse interests, and producing tangible outcomes. As such, **collaborative governance**, when intentionally structured and supported, can act as a **catalyst for institutional innovation** and **multi-actor engagement** in CET planning.

The energy transition towards collaborative governance in CET is also marked by the **emergence of new actors** in the governance landscape. Traditionally, energy and climate policies were the domain of national governments and public utilities. Today, a diverse constellation of actors - including energy communities, grassroots movements, start-ups, NGOs, and regional innovation agencies - are playing an increasingly central role in co-designing, implementing, and monitoring CET initiatives (AbdulKareem & Oladimeji, 2024).

These actors bring not only technical expertise and financial resources but also **social legitimacy** and **citizen engagement capacity**. Their involvement reflects a broader trend towards **polycentric governance** (Lofthouse & Herzberg, 2023), where authority is dispersed across multiple centers of decision-making.

This evolution is particularly evident in the domain of urban and mobility planning, as highlighted by recent studies on **people-centric approaches in smart cities**. In contrast to traditional, top-down models, these approaches emphasize **active citizen involvement**, co-creation, and participatory governance as key drivers of sustainable transformation (Trombin et al., 2020). According to the authors, the shift towards **decentralized, inclusive, and responsive governance structures** is essential to manage complex urban systems effectively and equitably.

Within this framework, **non-institutional actors** - including community groups, user associations, and local innovators - play an increasingly important role not only as beneficiaries but as **co-producers of public value**. Their engagement supports more adaptive and context-sensitive policy processes, especially in fields such as mobility, where behavioural change and social acceptance are fundamental for long-term impact.

The PLAN4CET project aligns with this perspective by promoting multi-actor governance and supporting municipalities in developing CET strategies that are not only technically sound but also socially grounded.

The incorporation of new actors into CET governance processes reshapes traditional **power dynamics**. As multiple stakeholders with diverse interests, values, and resources interact, governance becomes a site of negotiation, contestation, and potential conflict (Avelino & Wittmayer, 2016). Power is no longer monopolized by the state, but distributed among various entities capable of influencing outcomes, either through formal authority, technical expertise, or discursive framing.

Understanding these power dynamics is crucial to fostering governance arrangements that are not only effective but also democratic and just. The risk of elite capture, tokenistic participation, or the marginalization of vulnerable groups must be actively mitigated through institutional design and capacity-building (Brink et al., 2023). The PLAN4CET project addresses this by providing tools and technical assistance aimed at empowering local authorities while promoting inclusive stakeholder engagement.

4.1. Methodology

The focus of this study is placed on measures taken by cities contributing to setting up PEDs and Neighbourhoods for Sustainable Urban Development. Transforming cities is a necessary step for reaching the climate goals and decarbonization targets,. PEDs can be seen as an example of CET initiatives which involves a diverse constellation of stakeholders and which requires collaboration among them.

Reaching a full PED (for the framework definition of Positive Energy Districts please see the White Paper issued in 2021 by Joint Programming Initiative Urban Europe, [Positive Energy Districts \(PED\) | JPI Urban Europe](#)) is an ambitious goal therefore often research studies and results refer to 'PED relevant cases' instead. These are defined as "district-level experiences with high aspiration in terms of energy efficiency, energy flexibility and energy production" (Turci et al., 2021).

Examples of existing PED relevant cases can be found in the database compiled by the network on PEDs, COST Action PED-EU-NET ([PED DB: Map - PED-EU-NET | COST ACTION CA19126](#)). Note that the definition of PEDs is quite broad to allow for local implementations that can adapt to existing infrastructure and is meant to set a direction of action more than a strict set of rules to be fulfilled.

This study aims to shed light on the governance of PEDs by investigating processes, practices, and dynamics of collaboration among stakeholders involved in actions or projects whose result or goal contributes to building a PED or PEDs. Another interesting

aspect to be investigated is how leadership roles (informational, relational, and decisional) are exercised in these initiatives.

The geographical focus of the study is the Emilia-Romagna region, and more specifically the city of Parma. The city of Parma was chosen as it is a partner in the project PLAN4CET and contacts were easily available to the researchers. A total of **eight stakeholders** were interviewed, representing the **five-helix model**: 1 institutions, 1 citizens, 2 public administrations, 2 associations, and 2 enterprises. Participants were selected based on their knowledge of the topic and their interest in the field, with the aim of gathering perspectives from across different sectors.

As part of the research plan, particular attention was devoted to the identification and involvement of relevant stakeholders, in line with the overall objective of investigating the governance of PEDs. The link with CET is established through the Climate City Contract (CCC)¹, which provides the overarching framework connecting local climate strategies with the development of PEDs as concrete urban transformation projects.

For the selection of stakeholders, two complementary methods were applied. First, a list was compiled of actors who had already joined the CCC). Building on this initial pool, a **snowball sampling** approach was then adopted. This second method was particularly suitable given the research objective: to investigate the governance of PEDs. Indeed, during the first round of interviews, it emerged that certain actors had been directly involved in projects dedicated to the design and co-creation of a PED.

Data collection took place between **July and August 2025**, through **semi-structured one-to-one interviews (researcher-interviewee)** conducted remotely on the Microsoft Teams platform. Each interview lasted approximately one hour. The researcher, a sociologist by background with solid experience in conducting interviews, has been

¹ Climate City Contracts are strategic agreements developed within the EU Mission “100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030.” They set out each city’s pathway to climate neutrality by 2030, including clear commitments, governance arrangements, and an investment plan. CCCs are not legally binding but act as cooperation pacts between the city, the European Commission, national/regional authorities, businesses, academia, and citizens. They serve as a governance tool to align stakeholders, mobilize resources, and monitor progress toward climate neutrality.

involved in the project since its inception and is therefore well acquainted with its aims and objectives. A copy of the interview guide is provided in the appendix (Annex 1).

The interviews were analyzed qualitatively, using a **keyword-based approach** to identify recurring themes and differences across stakeholder groups.

4.2. Results

4.2.1. Interviews

The Road Towards the Definition of PEDs

The interviews clearly show that PEDs should not be understood as a purely technical outcome or a static goal, but rather as a **dynamic, multi-level process** that intertwines energy, urban, and social dimensions.

As INT. A observes, *“non si può pensare il PED come un risultato immediato, ma come un percorso: prima l'efficienza, poi le rinnovabili, poi il bilancio positivo”* (“a PED cannot be thought of as an immediate result, but rather as a pathway: first efficiency, then renewables, and finally a positive balance”). This perspective emphasizes the need for a gradual approach, with clearly defined intermediate objectives.

In the same direction, INT. D stresses that *“i PEDs non sono solo distretti energetici, ma processi di rigenerazione urbana che devono dialogare con le politiche territoriali e con le istituzioni che le guidano”* (“PEDs are not just energy districts, but processes of urban regeneration that must interact with territorial policies and the institutions that lead them”). Here, the political and governance dimension comes to the fore, positioning PEDs at the crossroads of energy transition and urban development.

From the private sector, INT. E highlights that *“il contributo delle imprese non può limitarsi alla fornitura di soluzioni tecniche: serve una partecipazione al disegno complessivo”* (“the contribution of enterprises cannot be limited to the provision of technical solutions: participation in the overall design is needed”). This enriches the definition of PEDs with the idea of private actors as co-creators, rather than mere implementers.

Civil society and associations also emphasize the social dimension. INT. F warns that *“senza il coinvolgimento delle comunità locali, i PED rischiano di restare esperimenti calati dall'alto”* (“without the involvement of local communities, PEDs risk remaining top-down experiments”), while INT. G adds that *“le associazioni hanno un ruolo fondamentale perché conoscono il territorio e le persone, e possono tradurre obiettivi complessi in azioni concrete”* (“associations play a fundamental role because they know the territory and the people, and can translate complex objectives into concrete actions”).

Finally, INT. B and INT. C draw attention to the operational capacities of local administrations: on the one hand, the risk that *“i progetti restino sulla carta”* (“projects remain only on paper”) (INT. B), and on the other, the need for municipalities to assume a *“ruolo di regia”* (“coordinating role”) (INT. C) without dispersing efforts.

Taken together, these insights portray PEDs as an **ecosystem of urban and energy innovation**, where multi-level governance, the active involvement of economic and social

actors, and effective communication strategies are indispensable. Not a single model, therefore, but a pathway shaped through cooperation among institutions, enterprises, citizens, and associations.

PEDs and Public Administration

The interviews reveal that public administration plays a decisive role in shaping the very **definition of what a PED is**. All three voices converge on the idea that a PED should not be seen as a static goal, but as a **dynamic process of urban and energy transformation**, structured in phases and supported by multi-level governance mechanisms.

INT. A remarks that *“non si può pensare il PED come un risultato immediato, ma come un percorso: prima l’efficienza, poi le rinnovabili, poi il bilancio positivo”* (“a PED cannot be thought of as an immediate result, but rather as a pathway: first efficiency, then renewables, and finally a positive balance”) (INT. A). This perspective highlights the role of public administration as the **director of the process**, responsible for translating European and national objectives into progressive and measurable steps.

INT. B emphasizes the gap between theoretical definitions and the operational capacity of municipalities: *“Il problema è che spesso i comuni non hanno personale o risorse dedicate, e i progetti rischiano di restare sulla carta”* (“the problem is that municipalities often lack dedicated staff or resources, and projects risk remaining only on paper”) (INT. B). This suggests that PED governance must be accompanied by **support mechanisms**—resources, skills, and coordination tools—without which the very definition risks remaining abstract.

INT. C further enriches the picture by underlining the importance of governance and communication: *“I comuni devono assumere un ruolo di regia, ma senza strumenti adeguati rischiano di frammentare gli sforzi”* (“municipalities need to take on a coordinating role, but without adequate tools they risk fragmenting efforts”) (INT. C). In this view, the PED is defined not only as an energy project but also as a **relational architecture**, requiring shared communication platforms, common languages, and structured processes of exchange.

In sum, the definition of PEDs emerging from the interviews places public administration at the center of a system of multi-level and multi-stakeholder governance. The PA is not only an implementer but also a translator, facilitator, and communicator. However, to fully play this role, continuous investment is required in **resources, competencies, and communication tools**; otherwise, the ambitious definition of PED risks remaining at the policy level without being translated into tangible transformations.

PEDs and Institutions

From INT. D's perspective, the relationship between PEDs, alliances, and institutions is not limited to the energy transition, but extends to the way urban and territorial policies are designed and governed. As he explains, *"i PEDs non sono solo distretti energetici, ma processi di rigenerazione urbana che devono dialogare con le politiche territoriali e con le istituzioni che le guidano"* ("PEDs are not just energy districts, but processes of urban regeneration that must interact with territorial policies and the institutions that lead them") (INT. D).

This highlights that institutions are not merely sponsors or regulators, but **strategic enablers**: they provide the frameworks, planning instruments, and legitimacy required to integrate PEDs into broader urban agendas. Without such alignment, PEDs risk remaining isolated pilot projects rather than becoming catalysts of systemic change.

INT. D also stresses the centrality of governance, observing that *"senza un chiaro riconoscimento istituzionale, i PEDs rischiano di restare esperienze sperimentali non trasferibili"* ("without clear institutional recognition, PEDs risk remaining experimental experiences that cannot be scaled up") (INT. D). This remark points to the importance of institutional commitment in turning local innovation into durable and replicable models.

Communication is equally crucial in this relationship. As INT. D notes, *"la comunicazione deve essere sia verticale, verso le istituzioni superiori, che orizzontale, verso cittadini e imprese"* ("communication must be both vertical, towards higher-level institutions, and horizontal, towards citizens and businesses") (INT. D). Institutions, therefore, are positioned not only as decision-makers but also as communicative bridges that connect global policy frameworks with local implementation and citizen engagement.

In short, the relationship between PEDs, alliances, and institutions, as seen by INT. D, is defined by three interdependent dimensions: (1) **integration** of PEDs into institutional policies, (2) **governance** that ensures recognition and scalability, and (3) **communication** that sustains dialogue across levels and actors. Institutions thus emerge as both guardians of coherence and enablers of innovation in the PED framework.

PEDs and Private Entities

From INT. E's perspective, private entities are not just technological suppliers or passive implementers but **active co-creators** of the PED ecosystem. As he notes, *"il contributo delle imprese non può limitarsi alla fornitura di soluzioni tecniche: serve una partecipazione al disegno complessivo, in cui il privato porti innovazione ma anche capacità di visione"* ("the contribution of enterprises cannot be limited to the provision of technical solutions: participation in the overall design is needed, where private actors bring not only innovation but also a capacity for vision") (INT. E).

This observation highlights a crucial governance aspect: PEDs require a **shared strategic architecture**, where private actors sit alongside institutions and civil society in shaping both goals and means.

INT. E also stresses the importance of building alliances that are **mutually beneficial**: *“le imprese partecipano se percepiscono un ritorno, non solo economico ma anche reputazionale, e se vedono un quadro istituzionale chiaro che dia continuità agli sforzi”* (“companies participate if they perceive a return, not only economic but also reputational, and if they see a clear institutional framework that ensures continuity of efforts”) (INT. E). This suggests that trust, stability, and institutional commitment are key drivers for private engagement.

Communication plays a central role here as well. According to INT. E, *“serve una narrazione che valorizzi il ruolo del privato non come soggetto esterno ma come parte integrante dell’alleanza”* (“a narrative is needed that values the role of the private sector not as an external actor but as an integral part of the alliance”) (INT. E). In this sense, communication becomes a governance tool: it legitimizes private involvement and frames it within the collective objectives of the PED.

In conclusion, the relationship between PEDs, alliances, and private entities—as articulated by INT. E—is defined by three dimensions: (1) **co-creation** in the design of PEDs, (2) **stability and trust** provided by clear institutional frameworks, and (3) **communication** that reframes private actors as strategic partners rather than external contractors. This highlights how the success of PEDs depends on the ability of governance systems to fully integrate private entities into their relational and institutional architecture.

PEDs and Civic Participation

Civic participation emerges as a structural element in the development of PEDs and their alliances. As highlighted in the interviews, *“senza il coinvolgimento delle comunità locali, i PED rischiano di restare esperimenti calati dall’alto, incapaci di radicarsi nei quartieri”* (“without the involvement of local communities, PEDs risk remaining top-down experiments, unable to take root in neighborhoods”) (INT. F). This perspective underlines the idea that PEDs must be grounded in the daily life of local communities, rather than remaining abstract policy tools.

Participation is also understood as a matter of legitimacy and trust. The same interviewee stresses that *“la partecipazione deve essere reale, non solo consultiva: i cittadini devono percepire che le loro opinioni incidono davvero sul processo”* (“participation must be real, not only consultative: citizens must perceive that their opinions truly influence the process”) (INT. F). In this sense, civic engagement becomes a mechanism of governance: it does not only ensure that PEDs respond to local needs but also sustains the credibility of institutions over time.

Communication plays a central role in this relationship. As observed, *“serve un linguaggio accessibile, che traduca i temi complessi dell’energia in messaggi comprensibili e collegati alla vita quotidiana”* (“an accessible language is needed, one that translates the complex themes of energy into messages that are understandable and connected to everyday life”) (INT. F). Such an approach reframes communication as a tool of empowerment, allowing citizens to move from passive recipients to active contributors.

Finally, civic participation is also associated with questions of equity and inclusion. As noted, *“la sfida è includere anche le voci marginali, chi non ha normalmente accesso a questi processi”* (“the challenge is to also include marginal voices, those who do not normally have access to these processes”) (INT. F). This remark highlights the responsibility of PED governance to open spaces for underrepresented groups, ensuring that the transition does not reproduce existing inequalities.

Overall, the relationship between PEDs, alliances, and civic participation emerges as multidimensional: it requires embedding PEDs in local communities, fostering meaningful involvement, designing accessible communication strategies, and guaranteeing inclusiveness. Civic engagement, in this view, is not an accessory but a cornerstone for building legitimacy, resilience, and long-term sustainability.

PEDs and Associations

Associations emerge as key mediators between institutions and citizens, bringing a **community-based dimension** to the governance of PEDs. As noted during the interview, *“le associazioni hanno un ruolo fondamentale perché conoscono il territorio e le persone, e possono tradurre obiettivi complessi in azioni concrete”* (“associations play a fundamental role because they know the territory and the people, and can translate complex objectives into concrete actions”) (INT. G). This statement positions associations as **interpreters of policy**, capable of bridging the gap between technical design and everyday practices.

Their role is not limited to dissemination, but extends to **trust-building**. As observed, *“quando un messaggio arriva tramite un’associazione, i cittadini lo percepiscono come più vicino, meno distante”* (“when a message comes through an association, citizens perceive it as closer, less distant”) (INT. G). This highlights how associations enhance the credibility and acceptance of PED initiatives, acting as trusted interlocutors in contexts where institutions may appear remote.

Communication again plays a central role. Associations stress the importance of informal channels, noting that *“non bastano i documenti ufficiali: servono momenti di incontro, attività culturali, linguaggi accessibili”* (“official documents are not enough: we need moments of encounter, cultural activities, accessible languages”) (INT. G). Here, communication is reframed not only as information transfer but as a **cultural practice**, enabling participation through familiar and engaging formats.

Finally, associations also embody the challenge of inclusiveness. Their activities often reach groups that institutional communication struggles to engage, ensuring that *“anche chi normalmente non partecipa possa avere voce”* (“even those who normally do not participate can have a voice”) (INT. G). This dimension underscores their role as **gate-openers** in the governance of PEDs.

In summary, the relationship between PEDs, alliances, and associations is defined by four functions: (1) translating complex objectives into local action, (2) building trust and credibility, (3) fostering communication through cultural and informal means, and (4) enabling inclusiveness. Associations thus emerge as indispensable actors in embedding PEDs within the social fabric of communities.

4.3. Conclusions and key recommendations

The interviews analyzed provide a multifaceted picture in which PEDs do not emerge as a mere technical target, but rather as a dynamic and multi-level process intertwining energy, urban, and social dimensions. The research question – understanding what type of governance is most suitable for the realization of PEDs – finds here a preliminary yet significant answer: PED governance should be conceived as a system of cooperation and distributed leadership, able to connect institutions, businesses, associations, and citizens.

On the one hand, the role of **public administrations** is central: they are called to act as coordinators in translating European and national objectives into progressive steps, while equipping themselves with the resources and skills needed to prevent projects from remaining on paper. At the same time, **institutions** are recognized as guarantors of coherence and scalability: without clear institutional recognition, PEDs risk remaining isolated, non-replicable experiments.

From the private sector side, companies emphasize their role as **co-creators**, which goes beyond the mere provision of technical solutions: their participation depends on trust, regulatory clarity, and the possibility to contribute to the overall vision. In parallel, **civil society** and associations highlight the necessity of genuine community engagement, which anchors PEDs in local contexts through accessible language, cultural activities, and the inclusion of marginalized voices.

A crucial point emerging across perspectives is the recognition of the **scientific knowledge base** as fundamental to any innovation project. The production, sharing, and translation of knowledge – technical, institutional, and social – provide the common ground on which effective alliances can be built. In this sense, PED governance cannot overlook continuous investment in research, training, and the dissemination of accessible knowledge, ensuring that innovation remains both inclusive and sustainable.

What cuts across all perspectives is the centrality of **collaboration and communication** as governance tools. Administrations need platforms for exchange and common

languages; businesses need narratives that legitimize their role as partners; citizens and associations need channels that make participation effective and meaningful. Leadership, in this context, is never monolithic: it is a **plural, situated, and relational leadership**, built on the ability to coordinate, translate, and mediate among heterogeneous actors.

In conclusion, the study of PED governance through the interviews shows that no single or pre-defined model exists: the most suitable governance is the one that emerges **through dialogue and cooperation among diverse actors**, enhancing local specificities and fostering mechanisms of trust, reciprocity, and shared responsibility. It is precisely in the quality of these interactions – more than in technological solutions alone – that lies the potential for PEDs to evolve from pilot projects into **resilient ecosystems of urban and energy innovation**.

5. General conclusions

The analysis presented in this report underscores that the clean energy transition is fundamentally a governance challenge. Collaborative inter-municipal approaches reveal the value of connecting municipalities across shared socio-demographic and territorial profiles, enabling them to transform individual limitations into collective strengths. Public-Private Partnerships demonstrate how hybrid governance arrangements can mobilize financial, technical, and social resources, while ensuring that innovation and investment remain aligned with public objectives. Finally, Positive Energy Districts provide tangible illustrations of how collaborative governance can be enacted on the ground, turning climate neutrality into a co-created societal project.

Taken together, these perspectives highlight the central role of the Quintuple Helix in shaping CET pathways. By engaging institutions, citizens, enterprises, associations, and public administrations in processes of co-design and joint action, the transition becomes not only more efficient but also more democratic and inclusive. The road ahead requires continuous investment in dialogue, trust-building, and capacity development. Yet the lessons from Parma, Navarra, and Skåne demonstrate that when collaboration is institutionalised across scales and sectors, European municipalities can move beyond isolated efforts and collectively accelerate the path toward climate neutrality.

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7. Annex 1

A1. Protocol interview

Contesto

1. **Mi può dire il suo nome e raccontarmi del suo lavoro/delle attività che svolge nell'ambito di ... ?**
 - 1.1. *Dove lavora,*
 - 1.2. *Con che ruolo,*
 - 1.3. *Di che tematiche si occupa,*
 - 1.4. *Quale percorso di studio e professionale l'ha portata ad occuparsi di queste tematiche.*

2. **Secondo la sua esperienza e la sua conoscenza, come definirebbe un Positive Energy District e quali sono i principali elementi che lo compongono?**
 - 2.1. *Elementi tecnologici*
 - 2.2. *Elementi di governance*
 - 2.3. *Elementi sociali ed ambientali*

Processo di attivazione di PED (Alleanza)

3. **Nel caso della città di..., mi è giunta voce dell'attivazione di un PED. Mi racconta di cosa si tratta, di quale è l'attuale struttura o forma del PED e di quale è stato il processo che ha portato ad essa?**
 - 3.1. *Come è avvenuta l'ideazione, la nascita e com'è l'attuale vita-gestione del PED?*
 - 3.2. *Quale è stato il processo? Quali le fasi, obiettivi, organizzazione/strutture del processo partecipativo*
 - 3.3. *Chi gli attori principali coinvolti, chi gli attivatori, come gli attori hanno partecipato, strutture partecipative più o meno formali/online-facetoface, chi e come è stato coinvolto (come sono stati selezionati e contattati? Come sono stati motivati a collaborare?)*

4. **Quale è stato il ruolo e la forma della collaborazione tra organizzazioni?**
 - 4.1. *Dopo aver organizzato il lavoro (obiettivo concreto da raggiungere), siete stati liberi di gestirvi da soli o facevate riferimento a qualcuno? C'era un responsabile della collaborazione e della consegna dei risultati a qualcun'altro o c'era flessibilità di portare avanti il lavoro autonomamente?*
 - 4.2. *Modelli di governance: Condivisione, Collaborazione/Cooperazione, Policentrismo/Centrismo*

Attori chiave

5. **Mi racconta più nel dettaglio chi è coinvolto in questo processo, quali sono le caratteristiche, le idee, le decisioni di questi attori?**

- Attori:
 - o Amministrazioni pubbliche e settore pubblico (pubblico)
 - o Società civile (sociale)
 - o Imprese e settore privato (privato)
 - o Società civica (civico)
- Eventuali attori che hanno avuto un ruolo predominante

6. **Mi racconta quali sono stati i ruoli, le responsabilità, le risorse messe a disposizione dai diversi attori nelle diverse fasi del PED?**

- 6.1. Divisione dei ruoli
- 6.2. Responsabilità
- 6.3. Risorse
- 6.4. Leadership

Luoghi fisici e online

- 7. **Quali sono i luoghi delle decisioni e i luoghi del PED?**
- 8. **Usate già piattaforme per la partecipazione? Potrebbe servire? Quali funzionalità potrebbero essere utili per la partecipazione?**

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